

An Analysis of Expressives Speech Act in 'Enola Holmes' Film

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ABSTRACT: Discourse analysis is the type of analysis where the main focus is on language use. In this study the researcher focuses on the pragmatic field by using speech act theory, particularly the expressive speech act theory by Leech and Norrick to analyse the discourse. The objective of this study is the researcher wants to find out the expressive speech act said by the prominent character in the film entitled *Enola Holmes*, the name of the prominent character is *Enola Holmes*. In order to find out the answer of this research, the researcher uses descriptive qualitative as a method. Descriptive because the researcher is trying to describe the expressive speech acts that found in this study and qualitative due to the fact that the data are in the form of utterances. There are 27 utterances that found in this study that consist of expressive speech act said by *Enola Holmes* in *Enola Holmes* film. The researcher also uses the script of *Enola Holmes* film as an object. The expressive speech acts that found in this research are; thanking, congratulating, welcoming, condoling, deploring, praising, blaming, and accusing. Whereas, the one and only expressive speech act that not found in this study is an act of apologizing.

KEYWORDS: speech act, expressive, enola holmes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The products that made by a language such as a film, song, poem, play, novel, drama etc. are known as text. Halliday & Hasan (1976, pp. 1-2) defined text into some criterias; that text is may be spoken or written and also known classified into a unit language in use that is not a grammatical unit like a clause or a sentence; and it is not defined by its size, text also is not something that is like a sentence, only bigger; it is something that differs from a sentence in kind, and text is best viewed as a semantic unit; a unit not of form but of meaning. Halliday&Hassan (as cited in Siasi, 2018) also stated that a text is a semantic unit and it has an internal logic relation and a crucial attribute of every text is its unity (p. 87).

A text is also known as a part of a language that can be contextually understood. The purpose and meaning of language spoken or written by a person can be understandable in the context of an utterance is known. In line with Yule's definition of context, she states that (as cited in Al-Sulaimaan & Khoshaba, 2017) context simply means the physical environment in which a word is used (p. 48). Context and the text itself are two things that always relate to each other. In addition, context and text are considered vital items in discourse analysis. The text is known as a discourse itself while the context is elements that affect the discourse. The latter statement is in accordance with Widdowson (1989) as cited in (Pranowo, 2020) he defines the contexts as "...those aspects of the circumstance of actual language use which are taken as relevant to meaning" (p. 257).

The fact that text and context are two things that cannot be separated from discourse analysis already told us that discourse analysis is an analysis of discourse or also known as a text; written or spoken. This statement is supported Wodak & Meyer (as cited in Neneng et al., Zubaidah, & Ardelia, 2018) stated that "discourse analysis focus not only on texts, spoken or written, as objects of inquiry but a fully "critical" account of discourse would thus require a theorization and description of both the social processes and structures which give rise to the production of a text, and of the social structures and processes

within which individuals or groups as social historical subjects, create meanings in their interaction with texts". It can be simplified that discourse analysis is a tool that used to study language use.

The language use can be found easily in sentences, conversations, monologues, utterances, poems etc. The things were mentioned before also considered as texts. The use of language in different texts will show the different language uses, functions, and contexts. Particularly, when people say utterances to express their mind they aren't only talking but they also do actions. The latter statement is in line with Schiffrin's statement (1994) that said "Language can do things – can perform acts – because people share constitutive rules that create the acts and that allow them to label utterances as particular kinds of acts" (p. 60). It can be concluded that the language use and context of a text or simply can be named discourse can be studied from pragmatic field using speech act theory.

Austin as cited in (Fadhilah et al., 2021) suggests that in uttering a sentence, a speaker is generally involved in three different acts: "locutionary act, illocutionary act, and perlocutionary act" (p. 154). Following Searle (1976) made a clear classification of illocutionary act, he classified it into directives, commissives, expressives, assertives, and declarations. To conduct a discourse analysis study, Schiffrin (as cited in Derin et al., 2020) described that there are "at least five different approaches, namely speech act, interactional sociolinguistics, ethnology of communication, pragmatic, and conversational analysis approaches" (p. 1).

The fact that discourse can be analysed using speech act theory, the researcher decided that this study focuses only on what expressives speech act that appears in film entitled *Enola Holmes*. Lonergan (1984) briefly described film as a "photographic process, involving the effects of light and chemical on sensitive paper" (p. 7). Furthermore Kusumarasdyati and Luo (as stated in Anggraeni et al., 2018) state that "... films provide exposures to the real language, used in authentic settings and the culture in which the foreign language is spoken" (p. 2). Grundy (2000: 53) as cited in (Al-Hindawi, 2018), states that a speech act is "the act or the intent that a speaker accomplishes when using language in context, the meaning of which is inferred by hearers". Searle (as cited in Syafitri, 2020) divides speech act into five categories; they are assertive, directive, commissive, expressive, and declaration (p. 3). Whereas Revita also stated expressives speech is the speech acts that express the speaker's feelings about themselves or the world (as cited in Syafitri, 2020, p. 3).

In this study the object that used by the researcher is the script of *Enola Holmes* film. Therefore the data in this study will be in the form of utterances that said by the prominent character in the film. The data in this study will be examined using Searle's expressive speech act theory. Leech as cited in (Aryasih et al., 2020) explained expressive is used to express or make the speaker's psychological attitude towards a state of affairs; e.g. thanking, congratulating, pardoning, blaming, praising, condoling, etc. (p. 5). In line with Leech's statement, Norrick as stated in (Tamam et al., 2020) differentiate expressive speech act into apologizing, thanking, congratulating, condoling, deploring and welcoming (p. 21). The theories of expressives speech acts stated by Leech and Norrick are going to be used to analyse the collected data in this study.

The study of expressives speech act already conducted by several researcher. The first one entitled "Categorizing expressive speech acts in the pragmatically annotated SPICE Ireland corpus" written by Patricia Ronan in 2015. The study conducted by Patricia Ronan showed the result that eight distinct subcategories of expressive speech acts are identified they are; agreement, disagreement, volition, offering thanks, apologies, exclamations, expressions of sorrow and greetings. The second previous research is the one that written by Harun Hidayat entitled "Expressive Speech Acts In *The Fate Of The Furious*" Movie" in 2018 using quantitative descriptive as a method to analysed the data, the researcher found two results in her study, the first one is the nine kinds of expressive speech acts which are apologizing, thanking, praising, blaming, welcoming, pleasure, like, dislike, and sorrow while the second result showed the syntactical realization of the expressive speech acts that were found by the researcher were declarative, interrogative and impressive.

The last previous research is “Expressive Acts Used By The Characters In The Fredrik Backman’s “A Man Called Ove” written by Evi Indar Wati in 2018 and descriptive qualitative as a method, the researcher found fifty two data of utterances which are showed that there are eight types of expressive acts. Blaming is the highest frequency used by the characters, then followed by accusing, apologizing, appreciation, cursing, greeting, praising, and thanking. So, it can be concluded that the most dominant types of expressive acts is blaming because the characters wants to find the others characters fault.

There are two reasons why the researcher chose expressives speech act, the first one because this certain speech act oftenly use by people in order to express their feelings. The next reason because the researcher wants to find out the context that shown in this certain speech act. Therefore, the researcher is interested in conducting a research with Searle’s expressive speech act theory as a main focus.

II. METHODS

This study focuses on the expressive speech act that appears in certain film that are used as an object in this study. Furthermore, in order to analyse and find the data, the researcher applies descriptive qualitative as a method. Descriptive because the researcher is going to describe the expressive speech act that found in this study. Whereas qualitative because the data in this study is not in the form of number but utterances, Creswell explained in (Armistany & Zamzani, 2019) defined qualitative research as a “method to explore and understand meanings by some individuals or groups of people ascribed to social or humanitarian problems” (p. 188). Whereas Lofland and Lofland furtherly have stated that “the primary data sources in qualitative research are words and actions; the rest are additional data such as other documents” (p. 189).

The data of this study are selected from a film entitled Enola Holmes. Enola Holmes film script is used as a source of data, specifically the utterances said by the prominent character, Enola Holmes. The film is realeased in September 2020, directed by the British director Harry Bradbeer. Enola Holmes is a mystery film that made based on the book written by Nancy Springer. This film briefly told about the young teenage sister of the infamous Sherlock Holmes, who went to London with intention to go after her mother who has disappeared.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is going to describe and analyse the data about expressive speech act that said by the prominent character in Enola Holmes film. The researcher, in this section, is going to discuss the classification of expressives speech act that found as data in this study.

According to Leech (1983) expressive speech act consist of thanking, congratulating, pardoning, blaming, accusing, praising, condoling, etc (p. 106). In line with Leech’s statement, Norrick (1978) differetiate expressive speech act into apologizing, thanking, congratulating, condoling, deploring and welcoming. From two statement above it can be concluded that expressive speech acts consist of thanking, apologizing, blaming, accusing, praising, congratulating, deploring, condoling, welcoming etc. The theories of expressives speech acts by Leech (1983) and Norrick (1978) are used to analyse the collected data in this study which is the utterances said by the prominent character, Enola Holmes. This study has found 27 utterances that considered as expressive speech acts said by Enola Holmes. The findings will be described below :

3.1 Expressive speech act of Thanking

The expressive speech act of thanking shows verbal politeness from one person to another. This expression appears as response to the previous activity that makes a person feel grateful about it. Thanking is kind of expression that used by people to show their gratitude toward something, such as compliment, happy memories, kind offer, etc. that done by another people to them. In this study there are six expressive acts of

thanking that found in utterances said by Enola Holmes. The researcher presented the three of five utterances that consist 'thank you' below;

Example a :

Sherlock : *You know last time I remember, you are quite a timid little thing. You had a pine cone wrapped in wool, dragged it with you wherever you went, calling it Dash. Someone told you that Queen Victoria had a Cavalier King Charles Spaniel called Dash and you decided you wanted the same. We could never persuade you to put any trousers on. Your bottom was always bare. I think that's all the memories i have.*

Enola : *Thank you. If you could now forget them all.*

Example b :

Lady Tewkesbury : *I don't care if you're from the Houses of Parliament. Leave this house this instant. (to Enola and the other detective)*

Enola : *Me too (realising). Thank you for having me.*

Example c :

Enola : *May I borrow your pencil? Thank you* (she said thank you to the Newspaper Seller)

From the three utterances above that said by Enola Holmes showed that all of them consist of phrases 'thank you'. The first 'thank you' (a) appeared in the dialogue between Enola and Sherlock, the former said her 'thank you' in the first place because she's glad her brother remembered the childhood memories of her but at the same time she embarrassed of it, it can be seen in the next sentence said by Enola 'If you could now forget them all'.

In the second utterance (b) showed that Enola was dismissed by Lady Tewkesbury from Basilweather Hall, it can be seen that the phrase 'thank you' said by Enola Holmes purely used as a manner, she didn't say 'thank you' to respond to her expulsion but she said 'thank you' because she grateful she could met the Lady Tewkesbury eventhough she was outcasted.

The last utterance (c) happened between Enola and newspaper seller in the London street, Enola tried to borrow the newspaper seller's pencil, she said her 'thank you' because she grateful the newspaper seller let her borrowed his pencil. It can be concluded that Enola said her 'thank you' in different manner and context.

3.2 Expressive speech act of Congratulating

This expression happens when somebody feels pleased and happy about someone's achievement of success. The second expressive act that found in this study is the expressive act of congratulating. People usually express their happiness when someone achives his/her life goals or something really pleasant happen in other people lives. In this study, the researcher found one expressive act that was said by Enola Holmes;

Example a :

Enola : *Congratulations, you finally look like the nincompoop you were born to be. (Enola said this to Tewkesbury)*

This utterance was said by Enola Holmes who saw Tewkesbury at the House of Lords, which was getting ready for his first meeting. Enola said 'congratulations' to Tewkesbury as her greeting to him whereas at the same time she teased him about nincompoop. Enola adressed Tewkesbury as a nincompoop at their first -not

very good- encountered because Tewkesbury is the Viscount Tewkesbury, the Marquess of Basilweather. Enola also said her congratulations to Tewkesbury because she was glad of what Tewkesbury were going to do.

3.3 Expressive speech act of Accusing

Accusing according to Leech (1983) is similar to blaming (p. 106). The former is an expression used by people to express their accusation of something bad such as fault and crime that happened to their lives done by other people. In this study, the researcher found four utterances of expressive acts of accusing said by Enola Holmes, however, the researcher only presenting two of which that consist of expression of accusing as follows;

Example a :

Mycroft : *I want you to be happy.*

Enola : *No. You want you to be happy. You want me controlled, because otherwise you think I will affect your standing.*

Example b :

Sherlock : *You disappeared. We have to know how far you would run.*

Enola: *I'm just a case to you, Aren't I? A curiosity. Is that why you're here. To pick my brains?*

Sherlock : *No.*

Enola : *or possibly you're feeling guilty.*

In two utterances above showed Enola's expressions toward his two brothers. The first utterance (a) showed from a conversation between Enola and Mycroft, her first brother. This conversation happened in carriage shortly after Enola caught by the detectives ordered by Mycroft. Enola's accusation was a response to Mycroft utterance that saying he wants Enola to be happy, however, Enola didn't feel all the things Mycroft already done to her was because he wants her to be happy rather Enola felt Mycroft wanted to controlled her so he would feel like powerful man. It can be seen from the 'word 'no' that considered as Enola's disagreement continued by Enola's accusation by saying 'You want you to be happy. You want me controlled, because otherwise you think I will affect your standing' where the utterances was completely opposite to the things were said by Mycroft.

Whereas in second utterance (b) that happened between Enola and Sherlock, Enola accused by saying and questioning these utterances 'I'm just a case to you, Aren't I? A curiosity. Is that why you're here. To pick my brains?' and 'or possibly you're feeling guilty' to her brother because she felt like her brother Sherlock didn't truly care about her, he only visited her because of the case or guilty.

3.4 Expressive speech act of Welcoming

This expression appears when someone friendly toward somebody else. According to Norrick (1978) welcoming is an expression where the speaker greeting the hearer in a polite and pleasant manner. The welcoming expression said by Enola Holmes. In this study the researcher was only found one example of this expression said by Enola, as follows;

Example a :

Enola : *Afternoon*

This utterance happened when Enola went to a small restaurant in London with intention to meet Edith because she was looking for her mother Eudora Holmes. The greeting 'afternoon' was said by Enola to the waitress in the resaturant.

3.5 Expressive speech act of Blaming

Blaming is an expression used by someone to say that something bad or their fault as somebody else's responsibility. This kind of expression usually stated when they in tight situation when something really terrible happened and they don't want to be someone that feels responsible for everything that might come because of it. The researcher only found one utterance said by Enola Holmes that consisted expression of blaming in it, which is;

Example a :

Enola : *you do know you've entirely ruined phase three of my plan? (blaming Tewkesbury)*

Utterance above was happened after Enola and Tewkesbury succeeded escaped from the man who ordered to kill Tewkesbury by jumping out of train. Enola snapped her question 'you do know you've entirely ruined phase three of my plan?' to Tewkesbury because she felt like he was the reason why the phase three of her plan didn't work out as it supposed to be. The expressive act of blaming can be seen from word 'ruined'. From Enola's utterance can be seen that she let out an expressive act of blaming in the form of question.

3.6 Expressive speech act of Condoling

Based on Norrick (1987) condoling is an expression used by someone to express their grief and sadness towards something bad that happened to someone else. Whereas Martinez explained that "condolences make manifest to others that we are aware that they are experiencing a misfortune and express our sorrow for being unable to help" (2012, p. 14). This study only found one utterance that consists of expression of condolences that said by Enola Holmes;

Example a :

Enola : *I never really knew my father.*

Tewkesbury : *My fathers dead too.*

Enola and Tewkesbury: *I'm sorry.*

The dialogue above happened in the middle of the woods shortly after Enola and Tewkesbury jumping out of train, in the middle of the woods Enola and Tewkesbury rested while at the same time ate the mushrooms cooked by Tewkesbury. In the dialogue above they talked about their father who already passed away, when they realised the misfortune that happened to both of them they uttered their condolences to each other by saying "I'm sorry". The latter is an expression used by people to let other people know their sympathy toward something bad that happened to them.

3.7 Expressive speech act of Praising

Praising is an expression used by the speaker to give a compliment about something or someone by saying nice things about it. Usually when someone praises something or somebody, he/she finds something about it pleasant to see or feel, they approve and admire what's in it/them. In this study the expressive acts of praising was found in four utterances said by Enola Holmes, as the researcher presenting the three of them below;

Example a :

Enola : *Oh, you tickle me, Viscount Tewkesbury, you magnificent Marquess of blooming Basilweather. and you're a cleverer boy than I perhaps gave you credit for.*

Example b :

Mycroft : *oh, dear God, look at the house.*

Enola : *isn't it wonderful?*

Example c :

Enola : *No, You look good. This is good.*

The first utterance (a) was said by Enola when she tried to find clues about Tewkesbury's plan in his tree house around the Basilweather Hall woods. When she found what Tewkesbury's plan exactly was, she was surprised that Tewkesbury was cleverer than she gave him credit for. The utterance (a) that consists of expressive acts of praising was said by Enola to herself because she was alone in the tree house. Whereas the second utterance of praising that was said by Enola happened in the carriage, she give her response in a question by saying 'isn't it wonderful?' to her brother utterance that talking about the holmes' house and Enola respond him with a question that explicitly praising the house. Following the third utterance (c) was said by Enola when she saw Tewkesbury who wore a suit at the House of Lords, getting ready for his first meeting. She compliment Tewkesbury who looks good in a suit.

3.8 Expressive speech act of Deploring

Norricks (1978) mentioned deploring as an expression where the hearer do something that affects the speaker negatively and ends up with speaker's strong disapproval, sadness and regret. In this study the utterances that consist of deploring as an expression was found in utterances. In this study the researcher only presents the two utterances below;

Example a :

Tewkesbury : *where is your destination? I'm going to...*

Enola : *London*

Tewkesbury : *well then shall we, um, stick together? If you like.*

Enola : *No. We'll get to London and go our separate way. Understood?*

Tewkesbury : *Understood.*

Example b :

Tewkesbury : *Don't I sound pathetic?*

Enola : *No.*

Two dialogues above showed utterances said by Enola that consisted of expressive acts of deploring showed that Enola clearly said her strong disapproval when she talked with Tewkesbury. The first one (a) showed that Enola disagreed by saying 'no' with Tewkesbury idea to go to London together while the second one (b) she disagree by saying 'no' too when tewkesbury asking if he pathetic or not. From two dialogues above can be seen that Enola spoke her disagreement about the things that said by Tewkesbury by saying 'no'.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, the researcher found there are 27 utterances that identified as expressive speech acts said by Enola Holmes. They are 5 utterances of expressive acts of thanking, 1 utterance of congratulating, 1 utterance of welcoming, 1 utterance of condoling, 6 utterances of deploring, 5 utterances of praising, 2 utterances of blaming and 6 utterances of accusing in the dialogue of Enola Holmes film. The one and only expressive speech act that not found in this study is an act of apologizing.

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